

Studies on Some Newer Enaminonitriles : Synthesis of 1-Amino-2-Cyano-4,4-Diamido- (N-Arylidene amino)cyclohexenes

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Several 1-amino-2-cyano-4,4-diamido(N-arylideneamino)cyclohexenes have been prepared by the Thorpe-Zeigler reaction of α,α -bis(β -cyanoethyl)-malon-di-(N-arylideneamino)amides which were obtained by the cyanoethylation of malon-di-(N-arylideneamino)amides. Their structures were confirmed by ir, uv and nmr spectroscopy.

CYANOETHYLATED compounds find a wide utility in the formation of heterocyclic systems¹. Stauffer *et al* reported the Thorpe-Zeigler cyclisation of cyanoethylated fluorene. The dicyanoethylated product of 1-tetralone undergoes intramolecular cyclisation to form substituted enaminonitrile². In continuation of our earlier work, we report the synthesis of a number of 1-amino-2-cyano-4,4-diamido(N-arylidene amino)cyclohexenes.

Reaction of I with acrylonitrile in the presence of catalyst 'Triton B' resulted in the formation of α,α -bis(β -cyanoethyl)-malon-di-[N-arylidene amino]amides (II; 1-17). These compounds (1-17) underwent Thorpe-Zeigler cyclisation in presence of sodium hydride catalyst to give 1-amino-2-cyano-4,4-diamido(N-arylidene amino)cyclohexenes (III; 18-34). The relative electrophilic character of nitrile group and acidity of methylene group α to the nitrile facilitated the cyclisation. The structure of the compounds (18-34) has been confirmed on the basis of ir spectra, which showed a stretching vibration band in the 2200-2280 cm^{-1} region ($-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and absorption band at 1471-1600 cm^{-1} due to $\text{CH}=\text{N}$ group.

In the enaminonitrile III, there is the possibility of tautomerism among structures A, B, C. The ir, uv and nmr spectral data support the structure A.

The infrared data for the enaminonitriles are listed in Table 2. All the enaminonitriles show a band for nitrile group in the 2170-2200 cm^{-1} region indicating a highly conjugated nitrile group. These bands occur at frequencies 60-80 cm^{-1} lower than those in the parent cyanoethylated compounds. The lowering of the frequency is due to the increased interaction between the n-electrons on nitrogen atom and π -electrons of α - β double bond and with the π -electrons of the nitrile group³.

Further support for the enaminonitrile structure A comes from the appearance of two bands in the N-H stretching region which is compatible only with a primary amino group ($-\text{NH}_2$).

Bands appearing at 1615-1165 cm^{-1} (Table 2) have been assigned to $-\text{NH}_2$ deformation. Asymmetric stretching bands appear at 3500-3120 cm^{-1} .

The compounds also show peak in the 1580-1620 cm^{-1} region due to $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$. It would be difficult

to reconcile the bands observed at 2170-2200 cm^{-1} for the compounds (18-34) with structure C since the $-\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{N}-$ group absorbs at about 2045 cm^{-1} .

The nmr spectra of III in CDCl_3 $\delta_{(\text{ppm})}$ showed broad hump at 4.65 due to two NH_2 protons and multiplets at 2.40 for four allylic protons.

The uv spectra also support the structure A for enaminonitrile and absorption maxima are given in Table 2.

Experimental

Melting points are taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer and nmr spectra were recorded on Varian A-60-D and Perkin Elmer R-32 spectrometers using TMS as internal reference.

Malon-di-(N-arylidene amino)amides: These were prepared by reported method⁸.

α,α -bis(β -Cyanoethyl)-malon-di[(*p*-hydroxy)benzylidene amino]amide: Malon-di-[(*p*-hydroxy)benzylidene amino]amide (0.01 mole) was taken in dioxane (20 ml) and 'Triton B' (2 g) was added. To this solution, acrylonitrile (0.02 mole) was added dropwise during 1 hr while the reaction mixture was kept at 20-30°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 5 hr at room temp. and neutralized with HCl and poured into ice. The solid mass thus obtained was crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 176°. (Found: N, 18.90. Calcd.; N, 18.83%).

The other compounds of the series were prepared similarly. The results are recorded in Table 1.

1-Amino-2-cyano-4,4-di-amido[(p-hydroxy)benzylidene amino]cyclohexene: α,α -bis(β -Cyanoethyl)-malon-di[(*p*-hydroxy)benzylidene amino]amide (0.03 mole) in pure dry benzene (30 ml) was taken in a flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer. To this, a

TABLE 1- α,α -bis(β -CYANOETHYL)MALON-DI(N-ARYLIDENE AMINO) AMIDE

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen % Found (Calcd.)
1.	4-OH Phenyl	176	75	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$	18.90 (18.83)
2.	2-Cl Phenyl	212	62	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$	17.40 (17.42)
3.	4-Cl Phenyl	204	70	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$	17.15 (17.42)
4.	4-NO ₂ Phenyl	206	63	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$	14.50 (14.68)
5.	2,4-Dimethoxy phenyl	182	62.5	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$	15.63 (15.67)
6.	Phenyl	206	78	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$	20.20 (20.78)
7.	Furfuryl	175	60	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$	21.35 (21.31)
8.	3-OH Phenyl	162	55	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$	18.00 (18.83)
9.	4-OCH ₃ Phenyl	182	65	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$	17.10 (17.78)
10.	4-N-Dimethyl phenyl	230	72	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$	16.90 (16.80)
11.	2-NO ₂ Phenyl	195	69	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$	14.70 (14.68)
12.	3-NO ₂ Phenyl	201	56	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$	14.05 (14.68)
13.	2-OH Phenyl	215	63	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$	19.00 (19.09)
14.	2-OCH ₃ Phenyl	198	67	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$	17.15 (17.78)
15.	2-CH ₃ Phenyl	200	55	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$	19.20 (19.09)
16.	4-OH ₂ Phenyl	217	58	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$	18.95 (19.09)
17.	Cinnamyl	187	61	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$	17.98 (18.02)

All compounds gave consistent C and H analysis.

TABLE 2—1-AMINO-2-CYANO-4,4-DI-AMIDO(N-ARYLIDENE AMINO)CYCLOHEXENE

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	IR stretching frequencies in cm ⁻¹			λ _{max}	ε _{max}
					C=N	C=C	CH=N		
18.	4-OH Phenyl	155	55	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	2182-2250	1615	1520	270	14,100
19.	2-Cl Phenyl	182-84	48	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	2182-2252	1585	1480	263	15,540
20.	4-Cl Phenyl	150	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	2195-2258	1595	1482	260	15,000
21.	4-NO ₂ Phenyl	113-15	45	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₆	2201-2260	1590	1495	265	16,980
22.	2,4-Dimethoxy phenyl	160	42.50	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₆	2195-2260	1592	1612	268	13,000
23.	Phenyl	132	48	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	2191-2250	1580	1500	270	12,560
24.	Furfuryl	142	40	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄					
25.	3-OH Phenyl	151	53	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄					
26.	4-OCH ₃ Phenyl	136	46	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	2195-2260	1600	1532	265	14,970
27.	4-N-Dimethyl phenyl	172	42	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄	—	—	—	261	15,600
28.	2-NO ₂ Phenyl	122	48	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₆	—	—	—	260	13,230
29.	3-NO ₂ Phenyl	210	47	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₆	2202-2259	1585	1490	264	13,000
30.	2-OH Phenyl	195-97	47	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄	2200-2252	1610	1510	270	15,210
31.	2-OCH ₃ Phenyl	130	48	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄	2198-2258	1610	1530	263	14,900
32.	2-CH ₃ Phenyl	165	52	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄	2190-2250	1590	1495	268	16,325
33.	4-CH ₃ Phenyl	152	49	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄					
34.	Cinnamyl	128	53	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄					

All compounds gave consistent C and H analysis.

slurry of NaH (2 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added. After complete addition, the mixture was heated at 90-100° in an oil bath for 3-4 hr. It was then neutralized with glacial acetic acid and poured into ice. The crude product thus obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 155°. (Found : N, 18.87. Calcd. ; N, 18.83%). IR $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$: 2182-2250 (-C≡N), 1615 (C=C), 1520 (-CH=N-) cm⁻¹ ; UV λ_{max} : 270 mμ ε_{max} 14,100.

References

1. J. S. SHUKLA, I. AHMAD and S. SAXENA, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1979, 41, 70.
2. D. A. STAUFFER and O. E. FAUCHER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 935.
3. R. THIÈRE and A. VAN DORMAEL, *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, 46, 7913i.
4. BALDWIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 3280.